

Pollen Project

MetaDocencia Team

This project was born in 2023 to open community pathways to train representatives of MetaDocencia in different communities, networks, and events and to recognize those who participate in the project for their contribution to the growth of our community.

The individuals we collaborate with externally multiply and enhance the implementation of MetaDocencia's values of inclusion, diversity, community, and versatility, articulating very valuable interdisciplinary trajectories to extend the networks of community work and participation in Open Science in Spanish-speaking regions.

The Pollen Project aims to incorporate more people to represent MetaDocencia in external communities, networks, and events, recognizing their contribution to our mission and vision while deepening their community trajectories in MetaDocencia.

Objectives

- Open community pathways to train representatives of MetaDocencia in different communities, networks, and events.
- Offer community journeys to expand participation in Open Science communities.
- Recognize those who participate in the project for their contribution to the growth of our community.

More information

- [Pollen project presentation](#)
- [More info about the project](#) (in Spanish)